

The logo for SYMBIOSIS features the word in a bold, sans-serif font. The letters 'S', 'Y', 'M', 'I', and 'S' are dark blue, while 'B' and 'O' are green. The letter 'O' is stylized as a circle containing a white leaf-like pattern. The background is light green with faint leaf patterns in the corners.

SYMBIOSIS

Deliverable 4.1

Transformative Insights and Strategies
for Biodiversity Monitoring
in European Railways

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3	UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	SPAIN
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the findings of a survey of biodiversity and habitat monitoring practices among transport infrastructure stakeholders in Europe, with a particular focus on the railway sector. Conducted under Work Package 4 (Task 4.1) of the SYMBIOSIS project, the study gathered 26 detailed responses from asset managers, operators, and environmental experts across the rail, road, and energy sectors.

Key findings include:

- Around half of respondents conduct habitat (58%) or biodiversity (50%) monitoring, with similar proportions in the railway sector (53% and 47%, respectively).
- Lack of internal expertise (55–75%) and cost (36–57%) were the most frequently cited obstacles by organisations that do not currently monitor, with these barriers particularly pronounced in the railway sector.
- Conformity with regulations and reporting to authorities were by far the most frequently cited purposes of monitoring, while operational motivations such as infrastructure resilience and safety were cited less often.
- Ad hoc surveys are more frequent than systematic monitoring, with a substantial proportion of monitoring carried out on a needs-based schedule (53% for habitat, 46% for biodiversity), often linked to regulatory obligations rather than ongoing programmatic monitoring.
- There is no standardised approach to monitoring that was evidenced across respondents, limiting the comparability of data across organisations and countries.
- There is growing interest, with a large majority of respondents (69% for habitat, 77% for biodiversity) reporting increasing organisational interest in incorporating monitoring data into planning, management, and reporting.
- Railway organisations showed higher priority for invasive species monitoring (71%) and have relatively high rates of centralised data storage and cross-departmental data sharing, providing a solid foundation for more systematic frameworks.

- While wildlife–train collision risk was not the most cited monitoring purpose, survey responses revealed that some organisations already collect roadkill data and deploy camera traps targeting medium- to large-sized mammals. This suggests that collision risk is an important operational concern but currently managed outside the scope of formal biodiversity monitoring.

These findings establish a baseline for the European transport sector and identify key gaps, notably in expertise, standardisation, and integration of monitoring into operations, that must be addressed. The report argues that overcoming these challenges will require action on three fronts. First, technological innovation, including remote sensing, automated monitoring, AI-assisted classification, and cost-effective sensor-based approaches such as passive acoustic monitoring. Second, data standardisation and integration: adopting interoperable data standards such as Darwin Core, building on existing frameworks such as the IENE/BISON handbook, and using ecological modelling platforms to translate monitoring data into actionable management insights. Third, a fundamental shift in culture and perception, whereby monitoring is recognised not merely as a regulatory obligation but as an essential source of knowledge for sustainable management, risk mitigation, and adaptation. Together, these advances would enable the sector to move from the largely reactive, obligation-driven approach that currently prevails to a proactive, evidence-based model for biodiversity and habitat management across transport infrastructure.

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INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity and habitat loss are accelerating worldwide at an unprecedented rate in human history (IPBES, 2019). Halting and reversing this decline requires urgent, systemic action and the active participation of all sectors of the economy, including the transport infrastructure sector. The Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022) and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, DG-Environment, 2021) set ambitious targets that require nations and industries alike to align their activities with biodiversity conservation and ecological integrity. Achieving these targets depends critically on systematic, standardised monitoring that can provide the evidence base to track progress, inform decision-making, and guide effective action across sectors and national boundaries (Gonzalez et al., 2023). Yet significant disparities persist in how biodiversity is observed and reported, with many sectors and regions lacking coordinated monitoring systems to meet information needs and generate the data flows required by such frameworks.

Despite growing evidence of the costs and risks associated with environmental degradation (Dasgupta, 2021; IPBES, 2019), infrastructure projects and their management rarely fully integrate the impacts of their activities on biodiversity and habitats. The most recent IPBES assessment on business and biodiversity (Jones et al., 2026) underscores this gap: all businesses depend on and affect biodiversity, yet fewer than 1% of publicly reporting companies currently disclose their impacts, and business actions to manage negative impacts have largely been driven by regulation. At the global scale, this imbalance is stark: financial flows with direct negative impacts on nature were estimated at \$7.3 trillion in 2023, while only \$220 billion was directed towards biodiversity conservation and sustainable use. The IPBES assessment also identifies transportation as one of the sectors with relatively high quantified direct impacts on nature (Jones et al., 2026). Within this sector, technical efficiency, safety, and cost tend to take precedence, and the approach to biodiversity remains largely reactive, with decisions driven primarily by regulations and constraints

imposed by authorities rather than by a proactive commitment to environmental stewardship. A fundamental shift in this paradigm is needed.

While this challenge applies across all transport modes, the railway sector offers a particularly compelling case for action. Railways, as the backbone of sustainable mobility in Europe, manage extensive linear networks that traverse diverse landscapes and ecosystems, and are uniquely positioned not only to monitor biodiversity at scale but also to actively protect and promote it. However, to fully realise this potential and integrate biodiversity considerations throughout the infrastructure lifecycle, from planning and construction to operation and decommissioning, collaboration between infrastructure managers and the biodiversity sector must be strengthened. Streamlining biodiversity and habitat monitoring would enable the sector to measure its impact on nature, track progress towards local and international targets, and develop early warning systems to mitigate risks and enhance biodiversity on assets and across surrounding landscapes. Achieving this will require a unified framework to standardise data collection, integrate biodiversity information into operations and decision-making, and enhance nature across infrastructure networks. To be effective, developing such a framework will benefit significantly from stakeholder and expert insights, as well as a thorough understanding of current approaches across the sector, establishing an essential baseline for identifying and addressing gaps.

Important groundwork in this direction was laid by the UIC [REVERSE](https://uic.org/projects-99/reverse)¹ project (Ecological Effects of Railways on Wildlife), which published a strategy and action for biodiversity (International Union of Railways, 2022) and Guidelines on Managing Railway Assets for Biodiversity (International Union of Railways, 2023). The project set out 13 strategic recommendations, including the need for cultural change to prioritise nature, the acquisition of specialist ecological skills, and the adoption of consistent and repeatable monitoring approaches. Critically, the assessment also revealed that while over 80% of surveyed railway companies reported monitoring some aspect of biodiversity, only 25% undertook systematic and repeated monitoring, with the majority responding that they

¹ <https://uic.org/projects-99/reverse>

conducted monitoring on an ad hoc basis to meet statutory requirements (International Union of Railways, 2022). Key constraints identified included a lack of resources, skills and knowledge, and the absence of a strategy or plan. This work established both a strategic vision and an initial assessment of the challenges facing the sector, but did not include a detailed, quantitative assessment of monitoring practices, methods, and data use across a broad cross-section of organisations.

In this report, we present the first such assessment, conducted under Work Package 4 of the [SYMBIOSIS](#)² project. This project brings together railway infrastructure managers, researchers, and environmental specialists to create an inclusive framework for the harmonised collection, curation, analysis, reporting, and integration of high-quality biodiversity data across the European rail sector. Work Package 4 pursues this goal through four highly integrated tasks: 1) Evaluation of current practices in biodiversity data collection and reporting; 2) Pilot testing of new approaches to promote standardisation; 3) Demonstrating best practices for integrating biodiversity data into asset management systems; and 4) Co-designing an inclusive framework for standardised biodiversity monitoring, analysis, and reporting.

Achieving the transformative change needed to halt and reverse biodiversity loss in the transport sector will require not only technological innovation and data standardisation but also a fundamental shift in how the sector perceives and values biodiversity monitoring. This report, the main output of Task 4.1, presents the survey design, results, and their implications for the sector's transition towards systematic, evidence-based biodiversity management. The findings establish a baseline that will inform subsequent SYMBIOSIS tasks, in particular the application of automated sensor technology (Task 4.2)³ and the development of a standardised best-practice methodology for biodiversity monitoring (Task 4.4)⁴.

² <https://symbiosis-transport.eu/>

³ Advancements in Automated Biodiversity Monitoring for European Railways

⁴ Recommendations for new approaches for standardised biodiversity monitoring.

OBJECTIVE, SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The primary objective of Task 4.1 was to assess current biodiversity and habitat monitoring practices across European railways and the wider transport sector, building on insights from the UIC REVERSE and BISON projects, and to outline a comprehensive framework highlighting opportunities for transformative change to enable improvement and standardisation across the European rail industry. Using an online survey, we evaluated: (i) methods and protocols used; (ii) motivation, purpose, and organisational attitudes; (iii) challenges, including costs and skill requirements; (iv) consistency, standardisation, and repeatability; and (v) data integration into decision-making and reporting. We aimed to identify gaps and barriers to harmonisation and propose innovative solutions by integrating new sensor technology (Earth Observation and ground-based) and AI-assisted approaches.

This assessment covers how habitat and biodiversity data are collected using various monitoring methods across all stages of rail operations: planning, construction, operation, and decommissioning. While the survey primarily targets European railway operators, it also captures responses from stakeholders in the road and energy sectors to provide a broader context. We also explored organisations' attitudes toward habitat and biodiversity monitoring, as well as the constraints and barriers to adopting standardised practices for data acquisition, analysis, and reporting.

This study provides an initial quantitative baseline with three key limitations. First, voluntary participation may have introduced selection bias towards organisations already engaged with biodiversity monitoring. Second, the survey relies on self-reported data, which may be subject to differences in how concepts and terminology are interpreted, particularly regarding what constitutes "monitoring" versus periodic environmental assessment. Third, although the survey provides detailed insights from each participant, our focus on railway operators, combined with our sample size ($n=26$), limits our capacity for in-depth cross-sectoral comparisons, and results contrasting the railway sector with other transport sectors should be interpreted with caution.

1. METHODOLOGY

1.1 SURVEY OBJECTIVES

To gather fundamental information on habitat and biodiversity monitoring, identify gaps, and gain insight into how data are integrated and used to manage, protect, and value nature on railway assets, we designed an online questionnaire based on five key objectives (Figure 1):

- 1) List the methods and protocols used to monitor habitat and biodiversity.
- 2) Identify the motivation and purpose of monitoring.
- 3) Identify specific challenges affecting habitat and biodiversity monitoring.
- 4) Learn about perceptions and attitudes towards the integration of monitoring standards.
- 5) Identify how monitoring data are used and integrated in decision-making and reporting.

1.2 QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE AND DEFINITIONS

To optimise completion and prevent fatigue, we adopted a parsimonious approach, carefully balancing the number of questions and ensuring relevance and logical flow throughout the questionnaire. This approach aimed to facilitate stakeholders' participation and increase their willingness to engage in our study and with the SYMBIOSIS project. To reduce ambiguity in the questionnaire's terminology and concepts, we included definitions of the three core concepts used in the questions.

- I. **Habitat:** *A place or type of site where an organism, population, or ecological community occurs naturally. This includes both natural and human-altered environments where species reside for part or all of their life cycle.*
- II. **Biodiversity:** *The variety of all living organisms, including diversity within and between species.*
- III. **Monitoring:** *An organised survey designed to collect data that can inform us of the status and changes [of habitats and/or biodiversity] over time and space.*

1.3 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

We distributed this survey to asset managers, operators, and environmental experts in the rail, road, and energy sectors. Participants were invited to contribute to the study from June to October 2025. Although we designed the questionnaire with a focus on participants in the railway sector, we used inclusive language to allow input from other sectors, such as road and energy. In our survey, we also asked participants about the motivation, purpose, and interest in biodiversity and habitat monitoring within their company.

Figure 1: General logic and structure of the survey

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To maximise outreach and participation, we used four complementary channels to disseminate our survey:

- 1) The [SYMBIOSIS](https://symbiosis-transport.eu/)⁵ project website.
- 2) Personalised emails.
- 3) professional newsletters ([EU-RAIL](https://eu-rail.com/)⁶).
- 4) social media ([LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/company/uicrail/?originalSubdomain=fr)⁷).

Dissemination via email and social media benefited from the established networks of key project partners (i.e., [FEHRL](https://www.fehrl.org/)⁸ and [UIC](https://uic.org/)⁹). The survey and data management plan for this study has received a favourable ethical opinion from the UKCEH Human Research Ethics Committee¹⁰ and was deployed on [Jisc Online Survey](https://onlinesurveys.jisc.ac.uk)¹¹, a platform that is GDPR-compliant and ISO 27001 standard-certified (International Organization for Standardization, 2022).

⁵ <https://symbiosis-transport.eu/>

⁶ <https://rail-research.europa.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/uicrail/?originalSubdomain=fr>

⁸ <https://www.fehrl.org/>

⁹ <https://uic.org/>

¹⁰ Ref. HREC0085

¹¹ <https://onlinesurveys.jisc.ac.uk>

2. RESULTS

Given the sample composition, with railway respondents constituting the majority (15 out of 26) and other sectors represented by smaller numbers, comparisons between all respondents and the railway sector should be interpreted with caution rather than as comprehensive cross-sectoral comparisons. The analysis presents patterns observed across all respondents and then focuses on the railway subgroup, examining its practices, challenges, and opportunities. The analysis is structured as follows:

- 1) Respondent demographics.
- 2) Monitoring (implementation and interest).
- 3) Methods for monitoring.
- 4) Data storage, management and availability.
- 5) Reporting.
- 6) Aims and purposes of monitoring.

2.1. RESPONDENT DEMOGRAPHICS

Overall, there were 29 responses to the survey, from which we excluded three: one was a duplicate, one was from a respondent who did not answer most of the questions, and one was withdrawn after the respondent had answered on behalf of an organisation that later provided its own response. This resulted in 26 detailed and independent responses, each provided on behalf of the respondent's organisation or company. The geographic spread of the organisations represented is essentially within Europe, with one exception from the China Academy of Transportation Sciences. The countries covered by our participants are: Austria, Belgium, China, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK (England). Of the 26 respondents, 15 (58%) work within the railway sector and 5 (19%) in the road transport sector. More than half of the respondents (15) work for companies that operate and manage assets (railways or roads), 5 for environmental consultants, 3 in academia (researchers),

and 2 for environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs). One respondent did not disclose his affiliation.

2.2. MONITORING (IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEREST)

Regarding monitoring practices, 15 of the 26 respondents conduct formal habitat monitoring and 13 conduct biodiversity monitoring. Notably, all 13 who conduct biodiversity monitoring also conduct habitat monitoring. Of the 11 respondents who do not currently conduct habitat monitoring, 4 plan to implement it in the future. Similarly, of the 13 who do not conduct biodiversity monitoring, 3 are planning to do so.

Focusing on the railway sector specifically, 8 of the 15 respondents conduct habitat monitoring, and 7 conduct biodiversity monitoring (Figure 2). Among those not yet engaged in monitoring, 2 of the 7 who do not monitor habitat are planning to implement it, and 2 of the 8 who do not conduct biodiversity monitoring are planning to do so in the future.

Figure 2: Monitoring adoption rates for habitat monitoring, biodiversity monitoring, and both, across all respondents (n=26) and the railway sector (n=15).

Among railway respondents who are not currently monitoring, the lack of expertise was the most frequently cited barrier. This was reported by 5 of 7 for habitat and 6 of 8 for biodiversity monitoring. Costs were the second most common barrier, cited by 4 respondents for both habitat and biodiversity monitoring (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Challenges: a) preventing habitat monitoring among organisations not currently monitoring habitat, for all respondents (n=11) and the railway sector (n=7); and b) preventing biodiversity monitoring among organisations not currently monitoring biodiversity, for all respondents (n=13) and the railway sector (n=8).

Perhaps more striking, 3 of 7 railway respondents who do not monitor habitat indicated that it was “not needed,” suggesting that the relevance of habitat monitoring to railway operations is not yet universally recognised within the sector (Figure 3).

Among the 15 organisations that conduct habitat monitoring, implementation dates ranged from 1996 to 2024, with nearly half (8) implementing it after 2010. Similar dates were reported for biodiversity monitoring (1996 to 2024), with 7 respondents implementing their surveys between 2010 and 2024. However, respondents' comments reveal important differences in how monitoring is understood and practised. One stated, "We will only carry out habitat monitoring if works are going to happen in that area. Overall monitoring is not happening at the moment," while another noted that monitoring occurred "only in cases where it was obliged due to EIA [Environmental Impact Assessment]." These comments suggest that the term "monitoring" is interpreted differently across organisations, and for some, it refers to relatively short-term survey work (e.g., bat or herpetofauna surveys) undertaken as part of a legal obligation rather than ongoing programmatic monitoring.

This interpretation is further supported by the responses on monitoring frequency: while some organisations follow annual or other regular cycles, a substantial proportion, 53% for habitat monitoring and 46% for biodiversity monitoring, conduct monitoring on an ad hoc, needs-based basis (Figure 4). This is consistent with the findings of the REVERSE project, in which only a quarter of surveyed railway companies conducted systematic and repeated monitoring, with the majority reporting that they monitor on an ad hoc basis to meet statutory requirements (International Union of Railways, 2022).

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Figure 4: Frequency of habitat and biodiversity monitoring for (a) all respondents and (b) the railway sector.

Among the 15 organisations that conduct habitat monitoring, just over half (8) do so internally, while 7 rely on external consultants. In contrast, biodiversity monitoring is more commonly conducted in-house: 10 of 13 respondents do so internally, while only 3 rely on external experts (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Responsibility for habitat and biodiversity monitoring, showing the split between internal and external delivery and the departments or expert types involved.

Notable differences were observed in monitoring frequency depending on whether activities were delivered internally or by external consultants (Appendix, Table S1 Q7). For habitat monitoring, in-house teams most often reported monitoring on an ad hoc, needs-based schedule (5 out of 8), whereas external consultants were more likely to follow regular

schedules (4 out of 7). For biodiversity monitoring, internally delivered activities were more frequently conducted on a regular schedule (6 out of 10): 2 respondents monitored annually, and 1 conducted continuous monitoring.

These findings suggest that the delivery model influences not only who conducts the monitoring but also how regularly and consistently it takes place. Among railway respondents who do conduct monitoring, a large majority reported having specific objectives with clear targets, 7 out of 8 (88%) for habitat and 6 out of 7 (86%) for biodiversity. This may reflect the sector's compliance-oriented, project-driven approach to monitoring, where regulatory compliance often requires well-defined goals and measurable outcomes.

2.3. METHODS FOR MONITORING

Respondents also reported on the methods used to collect habitat monitoring data. Ground surveys were by far the most common approach (12 out of 15; 80%), followed by remote sensing (7 out of 15; 47%) and third-party products (6 out of 15; 40% - Appendix, Figure S1).

Among those using ground surveys, vegetation surveys were the most frequently reported method (50%), followed by land cover classification (25%) and bespoke or hybrid approaches (25%). Remote sensing methods were split evenly between satellite and airborne imagery (50% each). For third-party products, respondents most commonly reported using land cover and habitat maps (both 67%), while airborne imagery was used less frequently (17%). Free-text responses further highlighted the diversity of approaches in use, ranging from manual aerial interpretation and national vegetation survey methods to government, with one mentioning the use of citizen-science datasets.

When asked whether habitat data collection follows a systematic protocol or design, the majority of respondents (9 out of 15; 60%) indicated that it does, while 2 (13%) said it does not and 4 (27%) were unsure. The specific monitoring protocols or designs used varied considerably between respondents, with no clearly standardised approach evident. This diversity of methods is likely to limit the comparability of data across organisations and countries, representing a significant challenge for future monitoring and reporting frameworks.

Despite this variability in methods, a majority of respondents (8 out of 15; 53%) do employ a standardised habitat classification system, while 4 (27%) do not and 3 (20%) were unsure. A similar pattern is observed for biodiversity monitoring: 11 out of 15 (73%) use a standardised classification, one does not, and three were unsure.

Responsibility for habitat monitoring was evenly divided, with half of the respondents reporting it as an internal function and half relying on external support (Figure 5). Where monitoring is conducted internally, responsibility most commonly sits within environment departments (6 out of 8; 75%), with a smaller proportion assigned to asset management and maintenance teams (2 out of 8; 25%). When conducted externally, consultant ecologists are the most frequently engaged (57%), followed by environmental experts (29%) and geomatic specialists (14%).

A similar pattern was observed for biodiversity monitoring. Internal responsibility most commonly lies within environment departments (7 out of 10; 70%), followed by management and maintenance departments (2 out of 10; 20%). When external support is used, it is provided exclusively by environmental or ecological specialists, indicating a high degree of consistency in the expertise applied to both habitat and biodiversity monitoring.

While a significant proportion of respondents reported relying on external specialists for habitat and biodiversity monitoring, a lack of expertise was nonetheless frequently cited as a barrier. This likely reflects limited internal capacity, with financial and logistical constraints limiting consistent access to specialist support even when external consultants are engaged. These findings echo the REVERSE project's identification of a lack of resources, skills and knowledge as key constraints on effective biodiversity management in the railway sector (International Union of Railways, 2023), and suggest that this gap has not been substantially narrowed in the intervening years.

In terms of monitoring frequency, habitat monitoring was conducted or updated on an irregular, needs-based schedule in most cases (8 out of 15; 53%), with 3 respondents (20%) reporting annual monitoring and 4 (27%) monitoring at other regular intervals (Appendix, Figure S1). Biodiversity monitoring followed a similar pattern, with nearly half of

respondents (6 out of 13; 46%) reporting irregular monitoring schedules (Appendix, Figure S2).

Most respondents reported having specific objectives and clear targets for their habitat monitoring programmes (11 out of 15; 73%), and a similar majority did so for biodiversity monitoring (8 out of 13; 62%). However, a notable proportion indicated that their objectives remained general rather than target-driven (habitat: 4 out of 15, 27%; biodiversity: 5 out of 13, 39%). This suggests an opportunity to strengthen monitoring frameworks by adopting clear, measurable targets, which would support comparability, accountability, and evidence-based decision-making, though potentially at the cost of more holistic, exploratory monitoring approaches.

Regarding the taxonomic focus of biodiversity monitoring programmes, mammals (69%), birds (69%), and plants (62%) were the most commonly monitored groups. Invasive and rare species were also frequently reported, at 54% and 46% respectively (Figure 6).

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Figure 6: Taxonomic focus of biodiversity monitoring programmes for all respondents (n=13) and the railway sector (n=7).

Reptiles and amphibians were monitored by 5 of the 13 respondents (39%), while only one respondent included insects among their focal taxonomic groups, a gap also noted in the REVERSE report (International Union of Railways, 2022), which observed that few railway companies monitor ecologically important groups such as insects and fish.

Interestingly, among the 7 railway respondents that conduct biodiversity monitoring, invasive species were the most frequently cited focus (5 out of 7; 71%), followed by plants, rare species, mammals, birds, and reptiles and amphibians (all at 57%).

The prominence of invasive species as a monitoring priority in the railway sector is likely related to the linear and highly connected structure of railway corridors, which can facilitate the spread of invasive vegetation, posing risks to infrastructure integrity and generating significant management costs. This finding is consistent with the REVERSE project (International Union of Railways, 2022), which identified invasive alien species management as one of the highest priorities for railway companies.

Of the 13 respondents who monitor biodiversity, 5 (39%) use automated systems, but only 3 provided details on the technologies they employ. These primarily involved camera traps, sometimes combined with AI-based image screening.

A large majority of organisations that monitor biodiversity (11 out of 13; 85%) use indicator species in their monitoring protocols. All named species were medium to large mammals, including bears, tigers, wild boar, wolves, ungulates, and other large carnivores. Several respondents noted that the choice of indicator species depended on the habitat type or on national and regional regulatory requirements. Notably, one respondent described a habitat-driven approach to species selection, explaining that, depending on the habitat type encountered, they assume certain species occur there or can establish themselves, indicating that some organisations already integrate habitat understanding into their biodiversity monitoring and link habitat condition to expected species assemblages.

The combination of camera-trap deployment and an exclusive focus on medium- to large-sized mammals as indicator species is notable. While traffic and passenger safety was cited as a monitoring purpose by a third of railway respondents, the risk of wildlife–train collisions was not prominently identified as a distinct driver of biodiversity monitoring. However, some respondents explicitly referenced wildlife mortality data: one cited “Fauna road kill” as indicator species, and another described their monitoring protocol as involving “collection of road killed data.” These responses, together with the widespread use of camera traps

targeting large mammals, suggest that collision risk is an important operational concern in the sector, one that may currently be addressed through wildlife monitoring activities without being formally framed or reported as biodiversity monitoring.

2.4. DATA STORAGE, MANAGEMENT AND AVAILABILITY

For the majority of respondents, habitat monitoring data are stored and managed through centralised Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and local files or maps (11 out of 15; 73%), while 3 (20%) rely on third-party data management. In one case, either no data management procedure was in place, or the respondent was unaware of one. Biodiversity monitoring data followed a similar pattern: most respondents (11 out of 13; 85%) stored data in local files, maps, or centralised databases, while only 2 (15%) relied on third-party systems.

In terms of data accessibility, habitat data were in most cases centralised and available to multiple departments (10 out of 15; 67%), while 4 respondents (25%) reported no systematic cross-departmental access and one was unsure. Biodiversity data were shared more widely: 10 out of 13 respondents (77%) reported cross-departmental access, 2 (15%) reported that data were not shared, and 1 respondent was unsure.

This difference in accessibility may reflect the regulatory, reporting, and stakeholder requirements typically associated with biodiversity data, which often necessitate wider internal visibility and cross-departmental engagement. Habitat data, by contrast, may more commonly be collected and used primarily for operational and asset management purposes, potentially reducing the perceived need for cross-departmental availability.

Within the railway sector, the majority of respondents who monitor habitat reported storing data in centralised GIS systems (5 out of 8; 63%), and a similar pattern was observed for biodiversity data, with 4 out of 7 (57%) using centralised databases (Appendix, Table S1 Q12). This may reflect the established data infrastructure of railway organisations, which have long managed complex logistics and spatially distributed networks in a highly regulated environment. Cross-departmental data availability was also high among railway

respondents: 6 out of 8 (75%) reported that habitat data are shared across departments, and 6 out of 7 (86%) reported that biodiversity data are shared across departments.

2.5. REPORTING

Among the organisations that conduct habitat monitoring, nearly all use their data in some form of reporting (12 out of 15; 80%). More broadly, across all 26 respondents, including those who do not currently monitor habitat, more than two-thirds (18) reported that their organisation shows increasing interest in incorporating habitat data into their reports, while 5 (19%) indicated no such trend and 3 (12%) were unsure. A similar pattern was observed for biodiversity data: 11 out of 13 organisations (85%) that monitor biodiversity include it in their reports; only one does not, and one is unsure. When habitat data are included in reports, half of the respondents indicated that reporting occurs annually. A comparable frequency was observed for biodiversity data, with 5 of 9 respondents reporting it annually. However, public access and disclosure of these reports appear limited: only two respondents provided links to habitat reports, and a third noted that theirs is “not open to the public.” Three respondents provided links to biodiversity reports, and one stated that reporting is internal only.

In terms of reporting audiences, the national government (75%) and internal stakeholders (67%) were the primary recipients of habitat reports, followed by the public (42%) and 25% to NGOs (Appendix, Figure S1). The distribution was broadly similar for biodiversity reporting, with national government (90%) and internal stakeholders (64%) as the main recipients, the public in nearly half of cases (46%), and 27% to NGOs (Appendix, Figure S2). Other recipients cited by respondents included clients, local authorities, and partner companies.

Within the railway sector, a notable difference was observed between habitat and biodiversity reporting. While 6 out of 7 railway respondents who monitor biodiversity (86%) include it in their reporting, only 5 out of 8 (63%) do so for habitat monitoring. This gap may suggest that habitat data in the railway sector are more often collected for operational

purposes, such as vegetation management or land use planning, rather than being incorporated into formal monitoring and reporting processes.

Among those railway respondents who do report, the range of audiences was broad. All 5 who report on habitat data include their national government among their recipients, while 4 (80%) report to internal stakeholders and to the public, and 3 (60%) to NGOs (Appendix, Table S 1). A similarly wide distribution was observed for biodiversity reporting, with all 6 reporting respondents citing national government and 5 (83%) reporting internally. This breadth of reporting audiences is consistent with the public accountability expectations placed on railway organisations as operators of critical national infrastructure.

Across both habitat and biodiversity reporting, respondents who indicated increasing interest in incorporating monitoring data into their planning, management, and reporting processes tended to have a broader and more diverse set of reporting audiences. This was the case for 66% and 72% of respondents for habitat and biodiversity monitoring data, respectively, and these organisations almost always included the national government as a key recipient. For habitat monitoring, 47% listed the national government as one of their primary reporting audiences, and a similar proportion reported to multiple recipient groups simultaneously, suggesting a more complex, externally accountable reporting structure. A similar pattern was observed for biodiversity monitoring, with 48% including the national government as a reporting audience and 48% reporting to more than one recipient.

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2.6. AIMS AND PURPOSES OF MONITORING

Across all respondents, conformity with national and international regulations and agreements was the most frequently cited purpose of both habitat and biodiversity monitoring (17 out of 26 in each case), closely followed by reporting to authorities (16 for habitat, 15 for biodiversity). These two purposes clearly dominate the rationale for monitoring across all sectors represented in the survey, suggesting that regulatory and accountability frameworks are the primary drivers of monitoring activity (Table 1).

Table 1: Aims and purposes of habitat and biodiversity monitoring, reported by all respondents (n=26) and railway sector respondents (n=15). Counts indicate the number of respondents citing each purpose.

Purpose	Habitat (all)	Biodiversity (all)	Habitat (railway)	Biodiversity (railway)
Conformity with regulations and agreements	13	12	6	6
Reporting to authorities	12	12	6	6
Infrastructure planning	6	7	2	3
Infrastructure maintenance	5	6	4	3
Traffic and passenger safety	4	6	3	3
Resilience of infrastructure	5	3	2	1
Public relations and social responsibility	4	4	3	3
Business decision-making	2	4	1	2
Operational effectiveness	3	2	2	1
Public health	1	0	1	0

Beyond regulatory compliance, a range of operational and strategic purposes were cited, though less frequently. Traffic and passenger safety, infrastructure maintenance, and infrastructure planning were each mentioned by roughly a quarter of respondents, while public relations and social responsibility, infrastructure resilience, and business decision-making were cited by smaller numbers. The relatively low prominence of operational

motivations, despite the obvious relevance of habitat and biodiversity management to infrastructure resilience and safety, may indicate that monitoring is not yet widely integrated into day-to-day asset management practices.

Within the railway sector, the pattern was broadly similar, with regulatory compliance and reporting to authorities again ranking highest (both cited by 9 of 15 railway respondents). Notably, traffic and passenger safety was cited by a third of railway respondents for both habitat and biodiversity monitoring, suggesting a direct link between ecological monitoring and core operational concerns. One railway respondent also cited “reduce mortality and increase connectivity” as an additional purpose, reflecting the potential role of railway infrastructure in ecological connectivity.

The dominance of regulatory compliance as a motivation for monitoring may also explain the high proportion of ad hoc, needs-based monitoring reported earlier (53% for habitat, 46% for biodiversity). The implications of this pattern for data comparability, strategic value, and the distinction between systematic monitoring and obligation-driven assessment are explored further in the Discussion.

3. DISCUSSION

Biodiversity and habitat loss are accelerating across Europe, and the transport sector — as a major driver of land-use change, fragmentation, and ecological disruption — bears a particular responsibility to understand and mitigate its impacts. Railways, while widely recognised as the most sustainable mode of land transport, manage extensive linear networks that intersect diverse landscapes and ecosystems. The REVERSE project (International Union of Railways, 2022) established a strategic vision for biodiversity on European railways and provided an initial diagnostic of the sector’s challenges but called for a more detailed and quantitative understanding of current practices. This study responds to that need, providing an initial baseline for monitoring practices across transport-sector stakeholders and a focused assessment of the railway sector. Given the sample

composition (15 of 26 respondents from the railway sector), the analysis should be read primarily as a detailed examination of the railway subgroup rather than a comprehensive cross-sectoral comparison.

The findings reveal that habitat and biodiversity monitoring across the transport sector remains limited in both scope and consistency. Only around half of respondents conduct habitat or biodiversity monitoring, and among those who do not, only a small proportion have expressed interest in future implementation. This may reflect either a limited perceived need or that persistent barriers, particularly cost and a lack of in-house expertise, continue to discourage uptake. The frequent reliance on external consultants, coupled with the widespread citation of expertise as a barrier, suggests that many organisations face a capacity gap that financial and logistical constraints prevent them from consistently bridging. Notably, the REVERSE project identified the same constraints, a lack of resources, skills and knowledge, and the absence of a strategy or plan, indicating that these structural barriers have persisted despite growing strategic awareness of their importance (International Union of Railways, 2022).

Among those who conduct monitoring, the findings indicate considerable variability in practice. A substantial proportion of monitoring activities, 53% for habitat and 46% for biodiversity, are carried out on an ad hoc, needs-based schedule rather than as part of a regular programme. This is consistent with the REVERSE project's finding that only 25% of railway companies undertook systematic and repeated monitoring (International Union of Railways, 2022). Our survey quantifies this pattern across a broader cross-section of the transport sector. Perhaps more fundamentally, survey responses suggest that the term "monitoring" is interpreted broadly across organisations, in some cases encompassing short-term, obligation-driven surveys rather than the systematic, ongoing monitoring envisaged by international frameworks. This inconsistency in definition has important implications for the comparability and strategic value of the data being collected. It also suggests that, for many organisations, what is reported as "monitoring" may more

accurately be described as periodic environmental assessment, typically triggered by regulatory obligations such as Environmental Impact Assessments (Alvarez et al., 2025).

The dominance of regulatory compliance as the primary driver of monitoring activity reinforces this interpretation. Conformity with regulations and reporting to authorities were by far the most frequently cited purposes across all respondents, while operational motivations, such as infrastructure resilience, safety, and planning, were mentioned less often. This pattern indicates that monitoring is not yet widely integrated into day-to-day asset management and decision-making, even when organisations recognise its relevance to their operations.

Within the railway sector, the picture is broadly consistent with the overall findings, but we noted some distinctive characteristics. Railway respondents showed a notably high priority for invasive species monitoring (71%), reflecting the sector's awareness of the risks posed by invasive vegetation to infrastructure integrity along linear corridors. The survey also revealed that wildlife–train collision risk, while not prominently cited as a purpose of biodiversity monitoring, is nonetheless addressed through operational activities such as roadkill data collection and camera-trap deployment targeting medium- to large-sized mammals. This suggests that collision risk is currently treated as a separate operational problem rather than as part of biodiversity and habitat monitoring. A comprehensive and standardised monitoring programme could bridge this gap by providing the ecological data needed to identify areas of higher collision risk, inform the design and deployment of targeted mitigation measures, and reduce the barrier effect that rail and other transport networks can represent to wildlife movement and connectivity.

Railway organisations also showed relatively high rates of centralised data storage (63% for habitat) and cross-departmental data sharing (75% for habitat, 86% for biodiversity), suggesting that the sector's established data infrastructure and regulatory environment provide a foundation on which more systematic monitoring frameworks could be built to streamline the integration of habitat and biodiversity monitoring into operations and decision-making. However, realising this potential will also require a shift in culture and a

broader recognition that monitoring is not merely a regulatory obligation but an essential source of knowledge for sustainable management, risk mitigation, and adaptation. The REVERSE project made this case explicitly, calling on the sector to “enable a cultural change to prioritise nature and the environment” and to embed biodiversity at every level of the business (International Union of Railways, 2022). Our findings suggest that this cultural shift has yet to take hold broadly, but the foundations, in data infrastructure, growing organisational interest, and early technology adoption, are in place. These aspects must be considered as important as regulatory compliance itself, promoting a proactive approach to biodiversity and habitat management rather than the largely reactive one that currently prevails across the sector.

Nevertheless, there are signs of a shift in attitude and ambition. A large majority of respondents reported increased organisational interest in incorporating monitoring data into planning, management and reporting processes: 69% for habitat and 77% for biodiversity (Appendix, Figure S1 and Figure S2). Among these organisations, those who already report on monitoring results engage a broad range of audiences, including national government, internal stakeholders, the public, and NGOs. This breadth of engagement suggests a growing recognition of the value of monitoring data beyond regulatory compliance, with reporting extending to wider societal accountability.

3.1. OPPORTUNITIES FOR TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE

The challenges identified in this survey, including limited expertise, high costs, ad hoc monitoring schedules, and a lack of standardised methods, are not insurmountable. The rEvERsE project highlighted the potential of novel technologies, including high-resolution satellite and drone imagery, LiDAR, automated acoustic and visual detection systems, and environmental DNA (eDNA) protocols, and called for their integration into a standardised monitoring framework (International Union of Railways, 2022). Since then, rapid advances in remote sensing, automated monitoring technology, and artificial intelligence (AI) have brought these opportunities closer to operational reality, offering transformative potential

to overcome many of the barriers identified in both the REVERSE assessment and the present survey (Figure 7).

Framework for AI-Driven Biodiversity Monitoring

Figure 7: Methodological framework to monitor habitat and wildlife through automated sensors and AI learning systems

Earth observation (EO) technologies, including satellite and airborne data acquisition, offer a scalable and cost-effective means of mapping and monitoring habitats across extensive infrastructure networks (Box 1). For the railway sector, where assets span thousands of kilometres of linear corridors traversing diverse landscapes, EO can provide consistent, repeatable, and spatially comprehensive habitat assessments that would be impractical to achieve through ground surveys alone.

BOX 1: EARTH OBSERVATION AS A NEW LENS ON TRANSPORT CORRIDORS

Earth observation (EO), specifically optical satellite imagery and airborne LiDAR, is poised to transform how transport infrastructure managers map and monitor habitats. Commercial satellites now deliver frequent sub-metre optical imagery, while Sentinel-2 satellites provide free 10m continent-wide optical coverage fortnightly, making repeatable, large-scale habitat assessment both feasible and affordable. Airborne LiDAR adds a third dimension, revealing canopy height, understory structure, and features invisible from above.

Crucially, many railway and road operators already hold substantial EO data. Collected for engineering purposes, so far these data remain an untapped resource for ecological insight. When coupled with AI-driven classification, these combined data streams can detect habitat change, map invasive species, and support near-real-time environmental monitoring across thousands of kilometres of linear landscape features (ecological corridors) at a fraction of the cost required for traditional field surveys.

Illustration of a) a hybrid 3D flythrough visualisation that combines high-resolution optical imagery with LiDAR-derived terrain and linear vegetation structure, and b) an interactive tool for exploring and assessing canopy connectivity in linear features.

The available combination of free satellite imagery, increasingly high spatial and temporal resolutions, and three-dimensional sensing makes it possible to detect habitat change, regularly monitor vegetation encroachment, and assess landscape connectivity at a fraction of the cost required for traditional field-based approaches (Luque et al., 2018; Pettorelli et al., 2014).

3.1.1. OPTICAL SATELLITE IMAGERY FOR HABITAT MAPPING

For terrestrial environmental monitoring, information collected through EO relates to the composition and condition of vegetation and substrate. Optical EO offers three complementary dimensions of information, spatial, spectral, and temporal, each contributing to our capacity to map and evaluate the landscape. The integration of recent, very high-resolution optical EO data and artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to transform environmental monitoring (Krejcar & Namazi, 2026), particularly for biodiversity and habitat assessments along transport networks.

The spatial detail of optical EO data (metre and sub-metre resolution) is key for habitat, plant and feature mapping along the relatively narrow transport corridors typical of railway and road networks. Using imagery that captures more types of light and tracks changes through the growing season can improve habitat maps and make it easier to detect subtle shifts in vegetation health and habitat structure (Figure 8). When combined with AI and recent advances in data integration and techniques that convert large-scale satellite data into fine-scale local information (Serra Gallego et al., 2025), EO products and ground data together represent a step change in how we acquire and integrate information. Satellite-based optical EO sensors now achieve spatial resolutions ranging from 30 cm to 3 m for multispectral imagery, with hyperspectral coverage available at 20–30 m. Cost-free Sentinel-2 data provides 10–20 m resolution fortnightly, sufficient for broad network assessments, while commercial providers deliver the sub-metre detail needed for site-level habitat mapping along narrow transport corridors. Commercial satellite constellations also offer daily or near-daily revisit frequencies, mapping the same areas and providing higher temporal resolution than Sentinel-2 alone. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs, aka drones) give additional flexibility, with adjustable altitude and speed to achieve the desired balance between coverage, resolution, and spectral detail, with timing fully controlled by the operator.

Figure 8: Comparison of a) land cover classification derived from 10 m spatial resolution Sentinel-2 imagery (Land Cover Map 2023), and b) from 3 m PlanetScope basemap imagery, for an area of southern Manchester including multiple rail lines.

It is important to note, however, that optical satellite image data coverage is limited by cloud cover, while airborne campaigns must avoid rain and strong winds. Data quality can also be affected by variable light conditions caused by cloud shadows. These practical constraints must be factored into monitoring schedules and data acquisition plans.

3.1.2. LIDAR FOR 3D VEGETATION STRUCTURE

LiDAR, using near-infrared laser pulses from aircraft, helicopters, or UAVs, complements optical imagery by producing high-resolution three-dimensional point clouds that capture vertical vegetation structure in centimetre detail. This includes canopy height, density, understory composition, and critical habitat features such as dead wood, water bodies, hedgerows, and woodland fragments (Box 1). LiDAR also produces intensity values for each point in the three-dimensional cloud, which, when calibrated, can be used to classify vegetation layers and distinguish healthy from diseased vegetation. Beyond ecological mapping, LiDAR supports monitoring of topographic and structural changes caused by natural processes or maintenance activities. Its repeatability and scalability enable long-term surveillance of environmental dynamics along extensive transport networks. An affordable alternative to LiDAR for three-dimensional surface modelling is oblique photogrammetry using UAV-captured overlapping images processed with Structure from Motion algorithms (Iglhaut et al., 2019), though this approach lacks canopy penetration. When integrated with optical imagery, LiDAR adds crucial geometric detail, offering multi-dimensional representations of ecosystems that support both habitat classification and biodiversity assessment.

3.1.3. LEVERAGING EXISTING DATA ASSETS

Importantly, transport infrastructure managers, particularly in the railway and road sectors, may already hold substantial EO data assets collected for engineering, safety, or asset management purposes. These include high-resolution aerial imagery, LiDAR, topographic surveys, and vegetation assessments. This existing in-house capacity represents a potentially overlooked resource for biodiversity and habitat monitoring. Data originally acquired for vegetation clearance planning, embankment stability assessment, or land boundary mapping could, with appropriate reprocessing and ecological interpretation, provide valuable baseline information on habitat extent, condition, and change over time.

3.1.4. AI-POWERED EARTH OBSERVATION ANALYSIS AND VISUALISATION

While acquiring high-resolution optical image and LiDAR data produces vast amounts of raw data, AI can provide the analytical power needed to translate it into ecological insights. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms applied to EO data can classify land cover and habitat types, detect anomalies in vegetation health, and identify individual plant species, including invasive species. These models can also perform automated change detection, enabling near real-time monitoring of environmental conditions (Pettorelli et al., 2025; Yuan et al., 2020). By fusing data from multiple EO sources, AI supports the creation of robust models that inform both operational and conservation decisions.

Innovations in 3D rendering and interactive web mapping now enable the transformation of complex spatial datasets into intuitive visual experiences, bridging the gap between scientific analysis and practical decision-making (see Box 1).

3.1.5. CAMERA TRAPS AND AI-BASED IMAGE RECOGNITION

Camera traps are among the most widely deployed automated monitoring tools and are already in use within the transport sector, as our survey confirmed. Traditionally used to detect medium- to large-sized mammals, modern camera trap systems, when combined with AI-based image recognition, can automatically process thousands of images, classify species, estimate abundance, and detect temporal patterns in activity. Such technology can dramatically reduce the time and specific expertise required for data analysis, directly addressing two of the key barriers identified in this survey. Along transport corridors, camera traps are often used to monitor wildlife movement, identify collision risk hotspots, and evaluate the effectiveness of mitigation structures such as wildlife crossings, culverts, and fencing (Clevenger & Huijser, 2011). Our survey highlighted the use of camera traps, mainly for monitoring medium- to large-sized mammals, although detection rates from fixed cameras can be limited for these groups (Jumeau et al., 2017). Nevertheless, sensor-based monitoring systems using images or acoustic data expand the range of taxonomic groups monitored, including insects which are absent from most monitoring programmes (Roy et al., 2024; van Klink et al., 2022).

3.1.6. ACOUSTIC MONITORING

Passive Acoustic monitoring offers a complementary approach, enabling continuous, non-invasive surveillance of vocalising taxa, including birds, bats, amphibians, and insects such as crickets and grasshoppers (Ross et al., 2023). Acoustic sensors (Box 2) can be deployed at relatively low cost across large numbers of sites and operate in conditions where visual detection is impractical, at night, in dense vegetation, or in areas with restricted access. Comparative studies have shown that passive acoustic monitoring can reduce person-hour requirements relative to field-observer surveys, with substantially lower costs over multi-year deployments (Markova-Nenova et al., 2023; Williams et al., 2018). Advances in AI-assisted sound recognition now allow automated identification of species from acoustic recordings, supporting the detection of rare or elusive species and enabling long-term monitoring of community composition and phenology. For transport infrastructure managers, acoustic monitoring can provide early warning of biodiversity changes, detect the presence of protected species before maintenance or construction activities, and help ensure regulatory compliance.

3.1.7. INTEGRATED MONITORING STATIONS

Integrated monitoring stations represent the next step in this technological trajectory (Box 2). The UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH), in collaboration with Network Rail and many other research institutes, has developed a fully automated biodiversity monitoring station for field deployment (Strong, 2025). Solar-powered and potentially interconnected, these stations can combine acoustic sensors for birds, bats, and insects with light traps for moths and camera traps for small and large mammals, alongside detailed weather data collection.

These data can be automatically analysed using AI-based image and sound recognition algorithms and transmitted continuously to a central data server. Such integrated systems demonstrate the feasibility of continuous, multi-taxa biodiversity monitoring at scale, with minimal ongoing human input, a model that could be adapted and deployed across railway and other transport networks.

BOX 2: AUTOMATED BIODIVERSITY MONITORING USING ACOUSTIC AND IMAGE-BASED SENSORS

Camera traps, acoustic recorders, and integrated sensor stations can now operate continuously with minimal human intervention, collecting data on species presence and activity across sites that are often difficult or unsafe to survey in the field (Besson et al., 2022). When paired with AI, these systems automatically process thousands of images and sound recordings, classifying species and detecting temporal patterns in activity. Passive acoustic monitoring alone can cut person-hour requirements compared with traditional field surveys. Fully integrated monitoring stations, such as those developed by UKCEH in collaboration with Network Rail, combine acoustic sensors, light traps, and camera traps in a single solar-powered unit, demonstrating that continuous, multi-taxa biodiversity surveillance at scale is within reach. These technologies do not replace ecological expertise; rather, they extend the capacity to collect standardised data across days, months, and seasons. This bridges the gap between ad hoc, obligation-driven surveys and the systematic monitoring required for effective biodiversity assessment and habitat management.

Images of a) [Wildlife Audio Recorders](#) for singing birds, b) a [UKCEH LepiSense system](#), an autonomous affordable option for night flying insect (moths) monitoring and c) a [UKCEH Automated Insect Monitoring system](#) that can be coupled with acoustic (birds and bats) sensors for integrated monitoring.

3.1.8. TOWARDS STANDARDISED AND SCALABLE AUTOMATED MONITORING

The combination of these technologies, camera traps, acoustic sensors, and automated insect monitoring systems, with AI-assisted data processing, offers a pathway towards continuous, standardised, and scalable biodiversity monitoring across transport networks (Besson et al., 2022; van Klink et al., 2022). Emerging edge computing approaches, in which AI algorithms run directly on the recording device, can filter and classify data in situ, transmitting only relevant events rather than raw data volumes, thereby reducing costs and enabling near-real-time ecological alerts. However, realising the full potential of automated monitoring will also require greater standardisation of hardware, sampling protocols, and data formats across deployments, an area where initial guidelines, such as those developed by the UK Acoustic Network (Metcalf et al., 2022), provide a useful foundation. By reducing dependence on specialist field expertise and enabling consistent data collection across sites and over time, automated monitoring can help bridge the gap between the ad hoc, obligation-driven monitoring that currently prevails and the systematic, evidence-based approach required for effective biodiversity assessment and habitat management. These technologies in no way replace essential expertise in ecology and environmental sciences; automated systems, however, leverage the ability to collect data across days, months, and seasons with very little human input beyond setup, maintenance, and removal. The temporal scale of data collection also allows us to correlate with management activity and changes in the surrounding environment. Such sensor-based monitoring could be coupled with environmental DNA (eDNA) to inform biodiversity and species presence from traces of genetic material in water, soil, or air samples (Altermatt et al., 2025). While still maturing, eDNA could offer a cost-effective sampling approach for biodiversity monitoring in drainage systems and water bodies along transport corridors.

3.1.9. INTEGRATING MONITORING DATA INTO OPERATIONS AND DECISION-MAKING

Data integration and modelling for evidence-based management represent a further, and equally critical, opportunity. The survey findings highlighted considerable variability in methods, protocols, and classification systems across organisations, and revealed that

while centralised data storage is relatively common, particularly in the railway sector (63% for habitat data), data comparability across organisations and countries remains limited. Addressing this gap will require not only standardised monitoring protocols but also consistent terminology and interoperable data systems that enable the integration, sharing, and comparison of diverse datasets, from field surveys and sensor networks to remote sensing outputs. Important groundwork in this direction has been undertaken by the Infra Eco Network Europe (IENE), which manages an online [handbook on biodiversity and infrastructure](#)¹² (Rosell et al., 2023), developed with support from the EU-funded BISON project¹³. This handbook provides a shared glossary, practical guidelines, and a structured framework covering the full infrastructure lifecycle, from planning and mitigation to monitoring and maintenance, offering a common reference point for terminology and best practice across transport modes and countries.

The adoption of established data standards, such as the Darwin Core (DwC) framework¹⁴, offers a practical pathway towards this goal. Darwin Core provides a common vocabulary for describing species occurrences, sampling events, and environmental contexts, enabling alignment with wider biodiversity information systems and European data infrastructures. For railway and transport infrastructure managers, adopting such standards would ensure that monitoring data, whether collected internally, by external consultants, or through automated systems, can be aggregated and analysed consistently across sites, organisations, and national boundaries. This is particularly relevant given that our findings show that monitoring is often conducted by a mix of internal teams and external specialists, using varied, often bespoke approaches.

Equally important is the selection of relevant and standardised indicator species and habitats that reflect ecological sensitivity and management priorities. The survey revealed that indicator species used in current monitoring programmes are almost exclusively medium- to large-sized mammals, chosen mainly on the basis of regulatory requirements

¹² <https://www.biodiversityinfrastructure.org/>

¹³ <https://bison-transport.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

or local habitat conditions. While these taxonomic groups are operationally relevant, particularly for collision risk assessment, a broader, more ecologically representative set of indicators, encompassing insects, birds, and plants, would strengthen the ability of monitoring programmes to detect meaningful environmental change and inform management responses.

Beyond data standardisation, advances in ecological modelling offer powerful tools for translating monitoring data into actionable insight. Spatially explicit simulation platforms, such as RangeShifter (Bocedi et al., 2021), can model how species and habitats associated with railway environments respond to environmental change and management interventions. By simulating species' range dynamics, dispersal, and population persistence in fragmented landscapes, such models can assess and inform how infrastructure development, habitat restoration, or mitigation measures influence ecological connectivity and species movement. When linked with biodiversity datasets and GIS layers through interfaces such as RangeShiftR in the R statistical environment (Malchow et al., 2021), these platforms become practical decision-support tools, enabling railway operators to explore management scenarios, from the effects of new lines and vegetation management regimes to the design of green corridors, and to balance operational efficiency with ecological resilience. The relatively high rates of centralised GIS-based data storage reported by railway respondents in this survey suggest that much of the spatial data infrastructure needed to support such modelling approaches may already be in place.

3.1.10. STREAMLINING HABITAT AND BIODIVERSITY MONITORING ALSO CALLS FOR A CULTURE SHIFT

Beyond technological innovation, however, the most fundamental transformation required is one of perception and culture. The survey findings clearly show that monitoring is predominantly viewed as a regulatory obligation, a cost of compliance rather than a source of strategic value. This reactive mindset limits the potential of monitoring data to inform and improve operations. A shift in this perception is essential: habitat and biodiversity monitoring should be recognised as a core component of sustainable infrastructure

management, delivering tangible benefits for reporting efficiency, infrastructure planning, asset maintenance, and risk management. Organisations that integrate monitoring data into their planning and decision-making processes stand to gain earlier identification of risks, from invasive species encroachment to wildlife collision hotspots, enabling targeted, cost-effective interventions rather than reactive responses. Monitoring data can also inform infrastructure design and maintenance schedules, support climate adaptation strategies, and provide the evidence base needed to demonstrate environmental performance to regulators, investors, and the public.

Streamlining habitat and biodiversity monitoring, through standardised protocols, shared tools, and accessible technologies, would not only reduce the burden on individual organisations but also enable cross-sectoral and international comparability. This, in turn, would support the development of early warning systems, facilitate benchmarking and knowledge sharing, and provide the robust evidence base that European policy frameworks increasingly demand from infrastructure operators.

The questionnaire also explored respondents' prior engagement with biodiversity-related initiatives conducted in partnership with UIC, specifically outputs from the REVERSE and BISON projects (International Union of Railways, 2022, 2023; Rosell et al., 2023). Of the 26 respondents, 8 (31%) reported having participated in at least one of these earlier initiatives: 5 in REVERSE and 4 in BISON. Engagement was somewhat higher among railway respondents, with 6 out of 15 (40%) having participated in at least one previous survey and the REVERSE report (International Union of Railways, 2022) being the most widely recognised (5 out of 15; 33%). Nevertheless, the majority in both the full sample and the railway sector had not previously engaged with either initiative, suggesting that the present survey has captured different participants. This brings additional perspectives into the assessment while a core of previously engaged respondents provides continuity with the evidence base established by those projects.

4. CONCLUSION

Building on the strategic vision outlined by the REVERSE project (International Union of Railways, 2022), this study advances our understanding of biodiversity and habitat monitoring in the transport sector in several ways. First, it establishes a quantitative baseline against which future progress can be measured, particularly as European policy frameworks increasingly require infrastructure operators to demonstrate biodiversity outcomes. Second, it confirms that the main barriers identified by the REVERSE group namely expertise, cost, and the absence of standardised approaches, persist. Third, it highlights the considerable diversity in methods, protocols, and classification systems currently in use, underscoring the challenge of achieving data comparability across organisations and countries. This inconsistency is also evident in the terminology and concepts used to define monitoring activities.

Most importantly, our study reveals a significant gap between organisational interest and actual implementation, a finding that aligns with the most recent IPBES business and biodiversity assessment, which concludes that current business conditions are insufficient to achieve the transformative change needed to halt and reverse biodiversity loss (Jones et al., 2026). Specifically, the IPBES assessment calls for the creation of an enabling environment through changes in policy and regulation, economic incentives, social values, technology and data, and capacity and knowledge, so that what is profitable for businesses also benefits biodiversity and society (Jones et al., 2026). For the transport sector, this means that streamlining biodiversity and habitat monitoring is not only a matter of technical innovation and standardisation but also of building the enabling conditions, including targeted support, shared guidelines, capacity building, and accessible tools to enable the transition from a largely reactive, obligation-driven approach to a proactive, evidence-based model for biodiversity and habitat management.

In summary, while about half of surveyed organisations conduct some form of habitat or biodiversity monitoring, current practices are ad hoc and obligation-driven rather than systematic, with no standardised methodology evident across the sector. Lack of internal

expertise and cost remain the most persistent barriers, particularly in the railway sector. However, increasing organisational interest in integrating monitoring data into planning and reporting, along with the railway sector's relatively strong data infrastructure and cross-departmental data sharing, provide a solid foundation for further development.

By establishing this baseline, this work offers a clear evidence base to guide future efforts. Engagement with key stakeholders has already begun through workshops and structured discussions, and this close collaboration will continue as we co-develop the frameworks and tools central to the subsequent SYMBIOSIS tasks: pilot testing of new sensor-based and AI-assisted monitoring approaches (Task 4.2), integration of biodiversity data into infrastructure asset management systems (Task 4.3), and co-development of a standardised best-practice methodology for biodiversity monitoring across the European rail sector (Task 4.4).

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APPENDIX

Table S 1. Breakdown of SYMBIOSIS survey responses from all respondents and from the subgroup associated with the railway sector. This analysis is divided into 13 thematic questions that focus on both habitat and biodiversity monitoring.

NOTE: Table S1 extends over multiple pages.

Table S1 Q1: How many of the respondents' organisations conduct formal habitat or biodiversity monitoring? And both?

MONITORING	All Respondents (n=26)	Railways Sector (n=15)
Habitat	Yes 58%	Yes 53%
Biodiversity	Yes 50%	Yes 53%
Both	Yes 50%	Yes 47%

Table S1 Q2: Among organisations that DO NOT currently conduct monitoring, how many are planning to implement monitoring in the future?

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	Yes 36%	Yes 29%
Biodiversity	Yes 23%	Yes 25%

Table S1 Q3: Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring, how often are they carried out?

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	20% Every 1 year	25% Every 1 year
	27% Other regular time period	38% Other regular time period
	53% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)	38% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)
Biodiversity	8% Constantly	14% Constantly
	15% Every 1 year	29% Every 1 year
	31% Other regular time period	29% Other regular time period
	46% Irregular (based on needs)	29% Irregular (based on needs)

Table S1 Q4: What methods do they use? Among organisations that currently conduct habitat monitoring.

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	80% Ground surveys	88% Ground surveys
	47% Remote sensing	50% Remote sensing
	40% Third-party products	38% Third-party products
Biodiversity	77% Standardised protocol	71% Standardised protocol
	39% Automated	42% Automated
	23% I don't know	29% I don't know

Table S1 Q5: Are there specific objectives for monitoring? Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring.

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	73% Specific	88% Specific
	27% General	12% General
Biodiversity	62% Specific	86% Specific
	39% General	14% General

Table S1 Q6: Are they done in-house (internal), or do they use external consultants? Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring.

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	Internal 53%	Internal 50%
	External 47%	External 50%
Biodiversity	Internal 77%	Internal 86%
	External 23%	External 14%

Table S1 Q7: Are there differences in method and frequency between those who conduct monitoring in-house (internal) and those who use external consultants?

MONITORING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	Internal	Internal
	13% Every 1 year	25% Every 1 year
	25% Other regular time period	25% Other regular time period
	62% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)	50% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)
	External Consultant	External Consultant
	29% Every 1 year	25% Every 1 year
	29% Other regular period	50% Other regular time period
	42% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)	25% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)
Biodiversity	Internal	Internal
	10% Constantly	16% Constantly
	20% Every 1 year	33% Every 1 year
	30% Other regular time period	16% Other regular time period
	40% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)	33% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)
	External Consultant	External Consultant
	67% Not following a regular schedule (based on needs)	
	33% Other regular time period	100% Other regular time period

Table S1 Q8: What are the challenges preventing organisation to conduct habitat and/or biodiversity monitoring? Among organisations that currently DO NOT currently conduct monitoring.

CHALLENGES	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	55% Lack of expertise	71% Lack of expertise
	46% Costs	57% Costs
	27% Lack of infrastructure	29% Lack of infrastructure
	37% Not needed	43% Not needed
Biodiversity	46% Lack of expertise	75% Lack of expertise
	46% Costs	50% Costs
	23% Lack of infrastructure	25% Lack of infrastructure
	31% Not needed	38% Not needed

Table S1 Q9: How frequently is reporting being done? Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring.

REPORTING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	50% Annually	60% Annually
	8% Other regular time period	
	25% As required / per project	20% As required / per project
	17% I don't know	
Biodiversity	31% Annually	67% Annually
	9% Other regular time period	
	47% As required / per project	17% As required / per project
	7% I don't know	

Table S1 Q10: Who are the primary recipients of the reports by the Railway sector? Among organisations that report on habitat and biodiversity.

REPORTING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	67% Internal	80% Internal
	42% Public	80% Public
	25% NGO	60% NGO
	75% National Government	100% National Government
	8% European Union	20% European Union
	Other 25%	
Biodiversity	64% Internal	83% Internal
	46% Public	67% Public
	27% NGO	50% NGO
	91% National Government	100% National Government
	0% European Union	0% European Union
	36% Other	17% Other (Local Authorities, Companies)

Table S1 Q11: Is there growing interest in including habitat or biodiversity monitoring data in the planning, management, and reporting processes?

REPORTING	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	69% Yes	68% Yes
	19% No	20% No
	12% I don't know	13% I don't know
Biodiversity	77% Yes	73% Yes
	23% No	27% No

Table S1 Q12: How are data stored and managed? Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring.

DATA MANAGEMENT	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	33% Centralised spatial database (geographic information system)	63% Centralised spatial database (geographic information system)
	40% Local files and maps	25% Local files and maps
	20% Stored or managed by third party	13% Stored or managed by third party
	7% No data management procedure in place	
Biodiversity	31% Centralised spatial database (geographic information system)	57% Centralised spatial database (geographic information system)
	31% Local files and maps	29% Local files and maps
	15% Stored or managed by third party	14% Stored or managed by third party

Table S1 Q13: Are habitat and/or biodiversity data available and used by multiple departments? Among organisations that currently conduct monitoring.

DATA MANAGEMENT	All Respondents	Railways Sector
Habitat	67% Data are centralised and available to multiple departments	75% Data are centralised and available to multiple departments
	27% Data are specific and not shared within the organisation	13% Data are specific and not shared within the organisation
	6% I don't know	12% I don't know
Biodiversity	77% Data centralised & available	86% Data are centralised and available to multiple departments
	15% Not shared	
	8% I don't know	14% I don't know

Figure S1. Summary of habitat monitoring practices across respondents, including monitoring uptake, methods, frequency, and data management.

Figure S2. Summary of biodiversity monitoring practices across respondents, including monitoring uptake, taxonomic focus, frequency, and data management.